

Thermodynamic Parameters of Pentaethylene glycol-Water System using Dielectric Relaxation Technique

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Abstract:

The dielectric relaxation measurement of liquid polymers (Penta-ethylene glycol) in water mixtures have been carried out over entire concentrations, at temperatures 25⁰C using picoseconds time domain reflectometry technique in the frequency range of 10 MHz to 30 GHz. The complex permittivity spectra of Pentaethylene glycol - water mixtures were fitted using Havriliak-Negami equation. The static dielectric constant (ϵ_0), high frequency permittivity (ϵ_∞) and relaxation time (τ) for all concentrations have determined using least square fit method. The thermodynamic parameters like free energy, enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) of activation for Pentaethylene glycol-water mixture were studied and reported.

Keywords: Liquid polymers, Dielectric Relaxation, time domain reflectometry, static dielectric constant (ϵ_0), high frequency permittivity (ϵ_∞), relaxation time (τ) free energy, enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) etc.

Introduction:

Dielectric properties of Pentaethylene glycol are useful for both fundamental studies and various industrial and pharmaceutical applications in our daily life. Due to remarkable properties and wide band applications, dielectric properties of Pentaethylene glycol and at various temperatures are attracting researchers.

Dielectric relaxation study on liquids provides information regarding their molecular behavior and dynamics of the molecules involved at dipolar level. Dielectric relaxation studies are useful in understanding the structure of polymers. Dielectric studies involve measurements of dielectric permittivity and dielectric loss. The measurement can be used to find dielectric relaxation times and distribution parameters. The relaxation time depends upon the molecular size, shape, intramolecular & intermolecular forces. Picosecond Time domain reflectometry

gives dielectric relaxation study over a wide frequency range [1-10]. Penta-ethylene glycol (PEG) is organic liquid and have two -OH groups at the ends of their molecular structure. Due to present of ends -OH groups, molecules of PEG can enter into intra & intermolecular hydrogen bonding giving rise to several conformation in water mixtures [11]. Dielectric relaxation & thermodynamic properties of PEG-Water mixture as a function of temperature and frequency have attracted much attention from industrial and academic researchers due to strong potential in industrial and biological applications.

In this paper we have reported the values of enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) of PEG-Water mixture, which will be useful for the researchers.

Experimental:

Material:

Penta ethylene glycol (PEG) was obtained commercially (Aldrich) and used

without further purification. The solutions were prepared at different weight fraction of water in PEG. The double distilled water is used to prepare mixtures. The dielectric spectra have been obtained by time domain reflectometry (TDR) technique. The Tektronix model no.DSA8200 Digital Serial Analyzer sampling oscilloscope along with sampling module80E08 has been used for the measurement. A repetitive fast rising voltage pulse with 18 picoseconds incident rise time was fed through coaxial line system of impedance of 50Ω. Reflected pulse without sample $R_1(t)$ and with sample $R_x(t)$ were recorded in time window of 2 nanosecond and digitized in 2000 points. The Fourier transformation of pulses and data analysis were done earlier to determine the complex permittivity spectra $\epsilon^*(\omega)$ using non linear least squares fit method [12,13].

Results and Discussion:

The frequency dependent values of dielectric permittivity (ϵ') and dielectric loss (ϵ'') of PEG-Water at 25°C are shown in Fig.1. It is observed from the plot that the values of dielectric permittivity (ϵ') decreases with increase in the frequency and dielectric loss (ϵ'') peak is obtained between 1 to 2 GHz.

In general dielectric loss spectrum of the aqueous solutions of Penta ethylene glycol exhibits an asymmetrical shape and described by the Havriliak-Negami

expression. We performed the non linear least square fitting procedure for polymers of ethylene glycol-water mixtures, in order to extract dielectric relaxation parameters with the following equation [14].

$$\epsilon^*(\omega) = \epsilon_\infty + \frac{\epsilon_0 - \epsilon_\infty}{\left[1 + (j\omega\tau)^{1-\alpha}\right]^\beta} \quad (1)$$

Where ϵ_0 is static dielectric constant, ϵ_∞ is dielectric constant at high frequency, τ is dielectric relaxation time, α and β are the distribution parameters. The value of α is kept zero and β is varied such that $0 \leq \beta \leq 1$. The values of ϵ_0 and τ for Penta ethylene glycol are studied.

Thermodynamic parameters:

The thermodynamic energy parameters ΔH and ΔS , for dielectric relaxation as rate processes for PEG under study were evaluated using Eyring's rate equations [15].

$$\tau = \left[\frac{h}{kT} \right] \exp \left[\frac{\Delta F}{RT} \right] \quad (2)$$

and

$$\Delta F = \Delta H - T\Delta S \quad (3)$$

where ΔF , ΔH and ΔS are free energy, enthalpy and entropy of activation for the dipolar orientation. The enthalpy and entropy of activation for PEG-Water mixture are reported in Table 1.

Table 1. Thermodynamic parameters of PEG-Water mixtures.

Wt. Fra. of Water	ΔH (kJ/mole)	ΔS (Jmol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)
0.0	23.16(181)	0.250(6)
0.2	22.78(133)	0.252(4)
0.5	20.62(78)	0.251(2)
0.6	13.80(116)	0.232(4)
0.8	11.48(174)	0.231(6)
1.0	17.60(42)	0.256(1)

Enthalpy of activation ΔH is the barrier to be surmounted in order to achieve group dipole reorientation in the primary relaxation process. Enthalpy of activation measured for PEG is found to be 23.16 kJ/mole. The values of enthalpies for PEG - water system are positive which suggest that the reaction is endothermic.

The entropy, ΔS , of a system is a measure of its orderly nature. If the environment of the system is cooperative for a particular process, the activated system becomes more ordered than the normal system and the change in entropy is negative. On the other hand, the positive values for the change in entropy indicate that the environment is not cooperative for a particular process and the activated system becomes less ordered than the normal system. The values of entropies for PEG - water are positive which indicates that the systems are less ordered. The value of entropy for PEG is found to be $0.250 \text{ Jmol}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$.

Conclusions:

The temperature dependent complex permittivity spectra of Penta ethylene glycol in aqueous solution have been studied using time domain reflectometry technique in the frequency range 10 MHz to 30 GHz. The variation in dielectric permittivity and dielectric loss with frequency indicates the structural dynamics of PEG. The variations between values of Enthalpy of activation ΔH and the entropy ΔS with weight fraction of water is reported.

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Figure 1: Frequency dependent dielectric permittivity (ϵ') and dielectric loss (ϵ'') for PEG-Water at 25°C.